

Verbal Expression and Mother's Desperation about Their Children with Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder

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ABSTRACT: Parents who have children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) are challenging because these children are special and need special treatment. Because they are challenging, parents need support from their inner or outer circle. One of the strategies to get a support is by expressing what they feel. Feelings can be expressed in various ways, verbal and non-verbal. It can be in a non-formal situation like having a conversation in a community or a home environment. Thus, this research aims to describe the verbal expressions and desperation of the mothers to raise their children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). This research uses phenomenological method called Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) because this study focuses on interpretive processes in understanding participants' experiences ideographically. 25 participants are observed and interviewed in-depth regarding their experiences in raising their children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). The participants' verbal expression of desperation are classified into seven themes: *Repeating the same instruction or warning over and over*, *Being different and isolated*, *Mess things up in the house*, *Could not stay still and unpredictable*, *Aggressiveness, irritation and tantrums*, *Extra effort for visual learner*, *Child lacks of motivation*. The results show that the feeling of desperation persistently happened because it is difficult to understand the characteristics of a child with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). The also admit that it is difficult to make normal children and mothers to accept their circumstances. Meanwhile, other participants state that they seek more information and knowledge about ADHD by joining a community to get help or support psychologically and medically, practice and more practice at home in order to help their children grow better.

KEYWORDS: Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder, Desperation, Narrative, Mothers, Verbal Expressions.

INTRODUCTION

A disorder that shows characteristics of lack of concentration, hyperactivity, and impulsivity and his/her development is not in accordance with his/her peers is commonly called Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. This disorder is found in an individual, especially children. These children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) have special conditions, such as being very active (hyperactive), impulsive and unable to concentrate well ^[15] This hyperactivity can be identified when the children are unable to sit still and quietly, often talking excessively, squirming in his seat, restlessness, running as he/she likes and unable to wait ^[1] when the child is at home or at school. Thus, many people around them condemned that the children who showed this condition are naughty or do not want to learn ^[2] The children who are diagnosed with this disorder surprisingly have poor perceptual motor skills^[28], thus, they experience developmental delays in daily activities and even their academic development becomes disrupted^[11].

The emotional instability of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) children exhibited by a child is a common feature of brain development disorders^[24] and is often associated with impulsive behavior although, according to a research, this emotional lability is most experienced by adolescents and adults with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) ^[25]. This Impulsive behaviour is the next major condition for Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). The children who showed this disorder often create confusion and act without thinking about the consequences^[2] and have difficulty participating properly, especially when the child is in a situation where they have to take turns with other children^[1]. The nature of children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) who are very aggressive or disruptive is a severe condition and tend to violate^[12].

The inability to concentrate, such as being seen as not listening, disorganized, not following instructions over and over, poor memory, and inconsistency at an unreasonable level, is the last major disorder condition in children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)^[1, 20]. In addition, children with ADHD who are diagnosed with certain learning disorders occur with seemingly negligent characteristics can be triggered by disappointment due to failure to do something (frustration), lack of interest, or limited ability^[1]. ADHD can affect four language axes in childhood and adolescence including delays in speech acquisition and language arrangement (mainly articulatory, phonological, lexical, and morphosyntactic as well as in the second, pragmatic), auditory processing disorders, speech disorders (speech, voice, and fluency), and deficits in linguistic processes involved in reading and writing and mathematics^[3].

A child is said to be diagnosed with ADHD if the child has at least six characteristics of each of the ADHD categories^[1]. According to a study, the involvement of mothers rated higher than fathers in the lives of their children who are diagnosed with ADHD^[6]. Therefore, this study will focus on mothers whose children are diagnosed with ADHD. Qualitative research on parents, especially mothers, and children with ADHD can be seen from the experiences of mothers in raising their children^[22], the pressure or stress experienced^[15, 10], also about parents' perceptions of their children who were diagnosed with ADHD and how they manage their children's challenging behaviours^[23].

Raising a child with ADHD is different compared to raising a child without ADHD^[26]. A study from Corcoran *et al*^[7] about a meta-synthetic and quantitative study that analyses a systematic review of qualitative studies of the life experiences of parents who have children with ADHD showed that anger and the desire to commit suicide existed due to the relentless pressure. In several other qualitative studies with the same objective found that the mothers experienced extreme sadness, shame that caused loneliness, guilt towards the child's siblings^[15, 5, 23]. The feeling of being demanded and isolated that made some mothers felt that home-schooling is the right solution for their children^[22] is often experienced by mothers and their children diagnosed with ADHD. Ringer *et al*^[23] explained that this disorder has a bad impact on those around him and put pressure on parents.

The feelings that appeared were the result of how difficult it was for mothers to raise their children with ADHD. For example, when the children destroyed the objects around them and it turned out the whole house is very messy. Other example is when the children were too active and have difficulty sleeping at night made their mother automatically stayed awake and would not leave their children alone^[5, 22]. Likewise, when the child tantrums, they will do something terrible and may injure themselves and their siblings. Therefore, as their mothers, they must remain vigilant^[5]. Sometimes the instructions given by the parents did not seem to be heard, or it seemed that the children have difficulty in interpreting the words spoken. A housewife also shared a story about her child who did schoolwork until late at night, and the worst story was when the child's homework was not finished at all. Other findings included financial problems, for example for the cost of therapy and therapists, home-schooling, special schools, and supplements for the child^[8]. A finding in the case of career mothers who had to rush to the office but she had to witness her child who was very slow in doing his work^[15].

In addition to having an impact on feeling, having a special child can also have a negative impact on the relationship around the mother and child. Firstly, the relationship between mother and father, for example quarrels happened because the situation at home is quite stressful^[15] to divorce because of the striking differences when raising a child with ADHD, yet the child's father is diagnosed with ADHD or has the symptoms^[8]. In other words, they did not fit when it came to raising their child. The relationship between the mother and the child's siblings who felt neglected because too much time has been taken up with their siblings with ADHD^[15, 5]. The relationship between mother and extended family who do not want to accept their children as they are. However, the findings in a study from Cosser^[8] showed both good and bad experiences. Some of the participants in the study said that they received support from their extended family. On the other hand, some participants stated that their extended family made things worse through their behaviour and speech. Another finding is that the extended family showed that as if nothing happened. Mother-teacher relationships that showed lack of good cooperation and empathy, and being judgmental for their children and teacher-student communication difficulties^[15]. The relationship between mother and mother of other normal children associated with the child's hyperactivity and has the potential to hurt other children. Thus, sometimes the mother is not invited to the event^[5].

Not only the mother, maintaining good relationships between children with ADHD and their peers at school or other environments is indeed one of the challenges for ADHD children^[27]. This challenge intersected with their non-ADHD peers who were often hurt because of the ADHD children's hyperactivity, resulted a social exclusion^[22]. Problem with siblings who were the victims of uncontrollable fights^[8] and violence by ADHD sibling^[5].

Another impact is on mother's mental health. Based on the findings of previous researchers, Moen *et al.* [17] stated that when the mother and father of the child have differences regarding the situation and development of the child with ADHD, then desperation arises. Other findings regarding persistent challenges related to children's behaviour such as temper tantrums, lack of concentration and ability to control impulsive behaviour, and poor delayed gratification for example when doing tasks that take hours^[21], thus causing a desperation. Another finding is about the use of drugs that may be a good option to reduce the child's symptoms regardless of the side effects. This option might help the mother because she felt so desperate about how to deal with her child who has ADHD that the mother immediately went to a place [medical practice] where she knows she will get treatment^[4]. Feeling of desperation is found in Wallace^[29] where the mother, because she was so desperate to face her child with ADHD, was willing to have her child taken by another mother. Based on this background, this study aims to describe the verbal expressions and forms of expression of desperation of mothers who have children with ADHD.

METHOD

This study is qualitative that produces descriptive data from participants with a narrative approach, which is based on someone's experience or story^[9]. This study used phenomenological method specifically in Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). The IPA approach was chosen because of its focus on interpretive processes in understanding participants' experiences ideographically. Participants in this study were mothers who were members of the ADHD parenting community. Before collecting the data, interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner. The researcher conducted an in-depth interview and gave a request: "Are you willing to be interviewed about your child?". If the participant agrees, it will proceed to the next question. "Could you tell us about your experience raising your child who was diagnosed with ADHD?" All interviews were recorded and transcribed.

The procedure to carry out this research was started by studying the narratives of the mothers from the results of in-depth interviews and then classified them according to the thematic classification. To analyse the data that has been found and successfully classified, the researcher uses thematic analysis of narrative data^[9]. After that, the report is made in the form of themes. Then sorted them out based on the themes about mothers' desperation in dealing with their children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD).

RESULTS

There were 25 narratives in Indonesian from 25 mothers who talked about their desperation in dealing with their children with ADHD. The research findings were classified into seven (7) themes, namely: *Repeating the same instruction or warning over and over*, *Being different and isolated*, *Mess things up in the house*, *Could not stay still and unpredictable*, *Aggressiveness, irritation and tantrums*, *Extra effort for visual learner*, *Child lacks of motivation*.

The number of findings of the narratives of the mothers as many as 25 and in Indonesian. The narratives contained in the results of this study are not the complete narratives conveyed by the participants, but are adjusted according to the needs of the study. The narration is delivered in Indonesian which is then translated into English without reducing or exaggerating the meaning contained.

Repeating the same instruction or warning over and over

Some mothers expressed their desperation about repeating the same directions over and over but their children have a hard time understanding the instructions. However, the mothers expressed that their children replied as if they understood but they did not. Thus this triggered the mothers' desperation about what they should do to make their child understand an instruction or warning. The following narratives were found in children who were hyperactive and have difficulty in concentrating (deficit attention). Besides, a mother is responsible for her child's safety. A mother expressed her desperation in giving the same instruction or warning to her son over and over when he screams and scatters toothpaste and soap especially after taking a bath. This action can harm the child:

He likes to run and jump. His body didn't move, but always screamed. He really likes to play with toothpaste, sometimes soap. If he finished bathing himself, the bathroom would be a mess. If I warned him not to do that again, he will say yes but he will repeat it again. (Participant 1)

The same two findings were found in two mothers who expressed that their children were also very active (hyperactive). The first mother expressed about the instructions given in order to remind her son for being not too active, her child agreed but it was repeated:

As for my son, he is very active but he's not naughty. However, if I warned him not to do that again [being very active], he will say yes but he will repeat it again. (Participant 2)

The second mother expressed her desperation eminently that made her too emotional, too tired and wanted to cry because her child was very difficult to be told or instructed on what the child should not do:

Why is it hard to tell a hyperactive children.. When he was told, he seemed to understand but he didn't. he still did things that were forbidden.. I'm tired, emotional, want to cry. (Participant 3)

Three findings from three mothers found that the child required extra effort when it came to do assignments. Whether be it less interesting or very important to the child, he still would not do it even though the mother had warned him repeatedly. For the first mother, the desperation was showed when the mother shouted at to the child, felt tired and even bored with the continuous repetition:

However.. some children with ADHD have different calculations.. If the task is less interesting (of interest), (somewhat) important, and requires a little effort (for example, getting rid of clean clothes and not throwing them on the floor), I can guarantee that the task will not be completed. I've been screaming, and repeating the same warning that I'm tired of repeating myself. (Participant 4)

The second mother showed the desperation because the instruction was about a very simple or common thing for children in general but it made her very desperate because her efforts to get her child to understand the instructions had not succeeded yet:

It's a matter of tidying clothes that made me annoyed. How to take clothes from the folds, how to hang them using hangers, how to separate dirty clothes. (Participant 5)

Interestingly, the following narrative on the third mother shed light on other mothers who feel desperate about this case. The mother conveyed that she has passed the difficult phases. She is very confident and suggests other mothers to give the child only short instructions. It will become even harder if we shout or scream:

.. My son used to be like that too.. [I] gave instructions over and over with the same words.. The harder we are, the harder he will be.. Just give short instructions.. (Participant 6)

Two other findings in two mothers felt desperate regarding toilet training. They sought a special trick so that their child are able to follow instructions related to the toilet. It can be concluded that what had been done in the past did not work:

I have a question, how do you do toilet training for ADHD children? is there a special trick or what should it be like? (Participant 7)

The second mother expressed bluntly how difficult it was to train her child to poop on the toilet. In this case, the mother seemed too ambitious because the child is still unable to do other simple things such as dressing. Undoubtedly, it will be much more difficult to move to a higher step especially toilet training. Surprisingly, it was told that the child was actually able to follow and understand specific instructions about going to the bathroom like peeing:

My son is now 7 years old, but he still pooped in his pants. it's really hard to train him... but if he wants to pee, thank God, he can go to the toilet because I tell him every hour or 2 hours to pee. My child can't take care of himself yet... he can't even put on his own clothes. (Participant 8)

Another finding regarding the repetition of instructions is about making eye contact. The mother said that whenever she instructed to make eye contact, the child often avoid it and if he is forced, he would immediately show disapproval, causing the mother to feel desperate:

My child often avoids eye contact. It wasn't that he didn't want to see, he seemed to be seeking comfort. So when I ask for a clear explanation, I ask him to make eye contact, he immediately shows an attitude of dislike. (Participant 9)

Bullying also happened in children with ADHD. In the following expression, it was the instruction or warning given by her child's friends. He was instructed not to be rude or at least her child knew how to play the game without hurting his friends. Thus, the child is often bullied, shunned, and ignored. Unfortunately, her child did not understand and did not care about it. The mother was so desperate because she witnessed and saw that her son was so clueless about what was going on:

Even if he was bullied, he didn't even understand. He kept on laughing and running.. When he and his friends were playing chase, he chased after them but he didn't know how to play, and in the end, he's being ignored. And he just ignored it and wandered off to another place. (Participant 10)

Being different and isolated

It is heart-breaking when a child is found different from other normal children, then they should be shunned. This phenomenon is very common among mothers whose children are diagnosed with ADHD. Apart from receiving reports or the child himself reporting that he is often shunned in child's play environment, it is also possible that the mother witnessed first-hand that her child was indeed being shunned. This is a very painful experience and it becomes a test in mother's life. The shunning was caused by the child who is very active and often disturbed other children. The child with this disorder did not understand what he had done; on the contrary, these normal children did not understand what was happening with their friend. Because of the desperation, the family even moved to one and other places for the sake of an environment that is able to accept her child as he is. In order that the child and her family feel comfortable. Sadly, it is still beyond expectations:

For me, every day is a test. Until we moved to another place looking for an environment that could accept my child's condition. Still, nothing is changed. My child is considered a nuisance by our neighbors. In the end, only my own family accepted my child's condition. (Participant 11)

In the following findings, it is the mother's desperation who witnessed first-hand that her child was completely shunned. They said that without her child, they could play comfortably. At last, the mother decided to keep her child away from normal children. By thinking that she will make sure her child is happy to be around her and remains strong:

I was at the point where my son was being ostracized from playing... one of my son's friends said 'why don't you just move, without you, we are all have fun.' But I'm just a human, sometimes there is also a time where I was at the point of exhaustion.. I hope I can always be a tough mom and still be able to make my child happy with me. (Participant 12)

The narrative expressed by a mother below showed a relief despite the child's shortcomings. Her child has followed a therapy for 1 year. He has a good memory that exceeds normal children. However, it was found that her child was indeed not able to socialize well with other children because he has not able to control his emotions. He tend to be annoying and was too selfish, thus, no child was happy or comfortable playing with him. Because of this desperation, the mother tried to find information or therapy to control the child's emotions:

My child has been on drug therapy for 1 year and has progressed rapidly. Besides that, my son has a very good memory even more than normal children... But unfortunately he can't socialize and all the kids of his age stayed away from him because he couldn't control himself, he was too selfish and nosy which made his friends are not happily playing with him... My question is, is there any therapy to control his emotions so he can socialize? (Participant 13)

The following narrative is a story about resentment and desperation of a mother. Take sides happened when complaints from normal children said that her child with ADHD like to steal his friends' toys, hit them and at the end her child was shunned. She expressed that her child was getting used to it, but if other (normal) kids did the same, they were fine, no complaint about it:

My son is 6 years old with ADHD. When he was playing with his friends, one of his friends reported that every time his friend holds something, my son will definitely take it, hit his friends but if the one who did it other than my child, they're just normal. I felt so sad sometimes. My son is used to being treated like that, but (as a mother) I am hurt. (Participant 14)

Mess things up in the house

One of the characteristics of children with ADHD is that they are very slow when they want to do something but are very reliable at destroying objects around them. The three mothers in the following narratives were so desperate but they must be patient with their child who loved to mess their house, slam and destroy things around him. The exhaustion of tidying up this mess is felt by the first mother:

My son often delays doing his work, our house is a mess. Not only the house is messy, but sometimes the stuffs in the bag, on the work desk, in the refrigerator are also scattered. I always feel overwhelmed with the chores at home like sorting out... (Participant 15)

Meanwhile, in this second mother's narrative, apart from her son often doing everything he liked to do, his son was also often rude to his sister. The desperation showed by the feeling of tiredness, emotion and wanted to cry badly:

I'm tired, emotional, want to cry. He's always rude to his little brother, always messing things up in the house..doing things as he pleases.. (Participant 16)

Instead of desperation, based on the following narratives, the mother actually tries to be a sincere, grateful and steadfast mother in order to help her child to grow better even though an incident such as breaking or slamming objects around him happened all the time:

My son used to always slam all kinds of things, break them.... Shouted until my ears were ringing... Trying to let go, being grateful and be as patient as possible may help my child to be better. (Participant 17)

Could not stay still and unpredictable

The content of the following narratives are mostly seen in ADHD children. Even though they are very common, mothers still felt desperate about their child's unpredictable movements:

It started with speech delay at the age of 3, and then I found out that my son was diagnosed with ADHD. My child jumped here and there, couldn't sit still (hyperactive), likes to bite anything, cries and laughs. He is very unpredictable. (Participant 18)

The following mother expressed the same thing. She said that her child sometimes showed strange movements and did not want to stay still, especially when the learning process took place at home. The child was able to sit still at home for only 30 minutes, after that he could be very active again until he could sit still quietly. This mother showed a good attitude by being a flexible and sincere mother in order to reduce the mother's desperation in dealing with her child with ADHD:

Sometimes strange movements also arise, like dancing. He can focus on his study for about 30 minutes, he did his assignments, but after that, he has to walk around first (can't stay still), then sit back down again doing his assignments. During this pandemic, because my child is studying from home, I'll just try to be flexible.

... but when he starts to look uncomfortable sitting and listening through the cell phone screen. I just let it go, he walks around the house. back and forth from the kitchen to the TV room, to the bedroom, etc., later when I see that he is in a good mood, I ask if he is ready to study yet. Usually, he actually wants to do his assignments / watch the learning videos from his teacher. (Participant 19)

Another narrative regarding the child's inability to sit still that exceeds the reasonable limit is found. Where the mother tried to endure instead of showing desperation when her child could not sleep and remained very active at night:

I just hold on to feelings of anger and irritation. It turns out that there is something similar with my story. Especially last night, he couldn't sleep, he wanted to play. (Participant 20)

Aggressiveness, irritation and tantrums

Behaviours such as being aggressive, very irritable, tantrums and unnatural are often experienced by mothers whose children have ADHD. The situation will be even more difficult for the mother when the child is not treated. Things that should not even happen but happened:

My son is still aggressive, if someone touches his toy, he will immediately get angry, then if someone gets angry he will be annoyed and he always takes it out on me by hitting me or pulling my hair. My child doesn't get any therapy, just as much as I can at home, the question is how to reduce his aggressiveness? Sometimes I also get overwhelmed with it. (Participant 21)

However, there is a possibility for a mother experienced desperation although her child is being treated. The child showed irritation during therapy. This therapy did not fully succeed to control his anger. Undoubtedly, the feeling of desperation is still there because the cost of therapy for ADHD children is quite expensive:

I am confused to deal with my child who is very irritable, as well as in therapy. If he was given an assignment and if he didn't want to do it, he would immediately get angry and shout. My child has been treated and received BT. At the beginning, there was a change in his ego that began to subside. But lately it's back again. This is the second time his ego has gone up and down. It will subside, not long after it goes up again. (Participant 22)

The mother's desperation and confusion in dealing with her child who often rages also occurred. If the mother is not able to contain her anger, then emotions will definitely explode because she does not know how to deal with or calm her child:

I have an ADHD child who often has tantrums, sometimes I am confused about how to deal with it.. if my child wants something, he is always angry. Sometimes I got emotional and being angry uncontrollably.. my child is 12 years old and is in 6th grade in a special school.. How should I deal with my child? I'm confused. He doesn't want to study anymore and what activities should I give him? (Participant 23)

Extra effort for visual learner

The inability to concentrate properly in children diagnosed with ADHD is also common. The child who is diagnosed with ADHD has difficulty in listening. A mother's experience in the following narrative is very inspiring, namely an endless effort expressed when the child is only able to learn by visual. The visual shown must be extraordinary. A picture or letter, for example, she must use a very striking colour of crayon. Being creative is this mother's choice. On top of that, the mother expressed that so many things had happened to reach the current state:

My child has difficulty in concentrating. Especially if he learns by just listening. He must see, he is a visual learner. I use the walls of the house as a learning tool, almost all of the walls I paste. At first, I pasted a picture then letters below it. If there is no suitable image, I will print a photo or I will draw it manually. Then the letters are written in bright coloured using crayons. Even when my son memorized the multiplication table, I wrote the numbers using crayons on white cardboard, and pasted it on the wall. (Participant 24)

Child lacks of motivation

The following narrative is a mother's experience who is desperately looking for ways to keep her child motivated both in terms of learning and hobbies. In accordance with what the mother expressed, her son was very happy when he left home, and from home to his tutoring place, but when he got there he was not motivated at all to do any activities, even activities that were in accordance with the child's interests:

The only thing I have a problem with is learning at school, my child looks fine when he wants to go to study from home but when he arrives, he is very moody, lacks of socialization and self-confidence.

Recently he asked for roller skating lessons, I have registered him to the club and bought the equipment. He was enthusiastic from home but when he arrived at the location, he did not want to follow the direction of his coach (only 8 meetings). At last, the coach laughed and said, "Oops, I am confused, how should I direct him?" (Participant 25)

DISCUSSION

Basically, this research is a study of parents' experiences, especially mothers, in dealing with their child with ADHD that have impact on the mother's mental health. The experience is categorized specifically, namely the narrative of mothers' desperation. This feeling of desperation in mothers often arises and is an impact of how hard and challenging it is to face a child with ADHD, especially in repeating the same instructions or warnings over and over. It can be seen from the expression that they often shout, annoyed and want to cry badly. Based on the findings above, that the expression of mothers' desperation over the repetition of instructions or warnings were found the most. This desperation appeared supported by the attitude of the children who seem to understand what the mother is saying but they did not. For the instruction section, the child's difficulty in following instructions is one of the special symptoms of inattention^[1]. Similar findings related to desperation in dealing with children's difficulties to follow instructions were found in^[17, 15]. However, a mother in present study shared her experience that short instructions were able to follow. It is not surprising that the narratives of mothers regarding the category of the child's inattention condition are mostly found because according to the scale findings of Lambek *et al.*^[14] that inattention is the strongest emotional support in parents.

Narratives about being isolated from the social life both the child and the mother are the second most common finding experienced by mothers. The mothers and their children with ADHD were ostracized because their children were so active that they hurt other children. This is align with the mother's social life who does not suitable with the environment as in the findings of Peters and Jackson^[22]. The mother who witnessed her child being bullied because her child is different reinforces the feeling of desperation by signalling without other children her child can be happy. In accordance with the results by Holmberg and Hjern^[13] stated that children who are diagnosed with ADHD are more often involved in bullying than other children.

The behaviour of children who liked to mess the house, damage things through tantrums and impulsive behaviour often makes mothers feel desperate. The same finding was found in Bullard^[5]. Mother's desperation about the child who does not want to sit still and unpredictable were also found in Mofokeng and Wath^[19]. Similar stories about the mother's desperation about her child being aggressive, very irritable and especially the child's tantrums are found in Moen *et al.*^[17] and Mofokeng and Wath^[19].

Coping with ADHD children, especially in the learning process is not easy. A mother in this study eventually succeeded in becoming a creative mother. Because children diagnosed with ADHD have difficulty understanding what is being heard, the mother chose to strengthen the child's visual abilities. Although definitely it will be very different from normal children, bright

colors are the best choice so that the child is able to recognize pictures and letters. This finding will be very useful because it can be used as an example by parents who often experience desperation during learning process, especially at home.

ADHD children who appear unmotivated and lack self-confidence can make the mother feel desperate. This desperation arose because it is the opposite that happened about learning outside their home, either at school or in tutoring. Children who are less motivated at school often result in moody, unable to socialize, and lack of confident. Bullard's finding^[5] about the motivation of ADHD children at home stated that even though parents has spent hours with their children doing their homework, parents still spared time to keep their children motivated. Finally, the child automatically chose to stay at home rather than spending time outside the house just because the child liked to play football.

CONCLUSION

Mothers who experience desperation when dealing with their children diagnosed with ADHD are common because their children are very different from other children. Their children are often ostracized from both the family and the environment. ADHD children who seem unmotivated and lack self-confidence also make mothers feel desperate. Lack of information and knowledge can be another factor that made them desperate to deal with their ADHD children. To overcome this, they can seek and join a community of parents who have children with ADHD. Joining a community is very beneficial because parents will not feel alone. By having the same experience, complaint or feeling, they will automatically support each other. Moreover, child's safety must be prioritized. Shouting or screaming at the children with ADHD will not help. Mothers must convince themselves that no more comparison with other normal children. Surrendering is not enough because it will only trigger a higher emotional level, for example, suicidal. Medical help may be urgently needed even though it is expensive.

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